

OTTER survey care professionals

Translated from Dutch to English

Version 1 was first filled in on October 14th, 2022

Version 2 was first filled in on November 23rd, 2022

Version log:

- 1) No registration form
 - a. In version 1 a registration form needed to be filled to receiving the link to the survey and attached the information letter. This was used to limit bot submissions.
 - b. In version 2 no registration was needed, to lower the barrier for participation. Participants could directly participate by clicking on the survey link.
- 2) The information letter is attached within the survey
 - a. In version 1 the information letter was received via email after registration in the registration form.
 - b. In version 2 the information letter was attached within the survey, since no registration form was present and no email was sent with an information letter.
- 3) Explicit captcha question was added
 - a. In version 2 an explicit captcha question ('I am no robot') was added to limit bot submissions.
- 4) Expire date after opening the survey link was set to 6 months
 - a. In version 1 the expire date was set at 1 week on default
 - b. In version 2 the expire date was extended to 6 months to limit the amount of incomplete submissions
- 5) The word 'proefpersonenbrief' was replaced by the word 'informatiebrief'

The questions in the survey version 2 stayed the same compared to version 1. Only the consent form (first page in the survey) was adjusted. Only version 2 is included below.

Communication- and BCI-needs in children and young adults with severe cerebral palsy

Some children and young adults with severe cerebral palsy (CP) are so motorically impaired that they have difficulty speaking and communicating. Researchers work on a new technique, named Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs), with which one could communicate via brain signals. Therefore, no movement, such as gestures and/or intelligible speech, is needed to communicate. We want to map what children (8 until and including 12 years old) and young adults (13 until and including 25 years old) with severe CP want and/or need in the field of communication and whether BCIs would be interesting for them.

In the link below you find the information letter with explanation about this study:
[E1 e2 informatiebrief toestemmingsformulier zorgprofessionals v1.0 050922 clean](#)

This survey consist of three parts:

- Demographical data
- Communication problems and communication aids
- Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs)

The survey is anonymous and takes about **20 minutes**.

We thank you in advance for your time.

I give consent to store my personal data for 30 years and to use it for future research in the field of CP, communication and BCIs.

Yes No

I give consent to make my coded research data publicly available on the internet, when an article is published with these data.

Yes No

Please click here to indicate that you are no robot.

By clicking on 'next' you indicate you understood the information letter and you give consent for participation in this study and for the use of your data in the way described in the information letter.

Part 1: Demographic data

[Q1] Your age:

[Q2] Your gender:

Male Female I prefer not to tell

[Q3] What is your highest level of education you received?

	V
Primary school	
Secondary education	
Secondary vocational education level 1, 2 or 3	
Secondary vocational education level 4	
Higher vocational education (polytechnics / university of applied science), Bachelor	
Higher vocational education (polytechnics / university of applied science), Master	
Scientific/academic education (university), Bachelor	
Scientific/academic education (university), Master	
PhD	
If you have another highest level of education, then you may enter this in the next question	

[Q3a] [If 'If you have another highest level of education, then you may enter this in the next question'] What is your highest level of education you received?

[Q4] Do or did you have a direct pedagogical or treatment relationship with not or barely speaking children and/or young adults age between 8 until and including 25 years old with CP (GMFCS level IV and/or V)?

GMFCS stands for Gross Motor Function Classification System.

- Yes, I work with this target group at this moment
 Yes, I worked with this target group in the past
 No, I did/do not have a direct pedagogical and/or treatment relationship with this target group

[If Q4 is 'No, I did/do not have a direct pedagogical and/or treatment relationship with this target']

Thank you for filling in this survey.

The remainder of this survey is aimed care professionals who work of worked with not or barely speaking children/young adults (8 until and including 25 years old) with CP (GMFCS IV and/or V).

From here onwards, the survey focusses on the (not or barely speaking) children and/or young adults (8 until and including 25 years old) with CP GMFCS IV and/or V whom you work(ed) with. Further in this survey these children/young adults will be referred to as 'this target group'.

[Q4a] [If Q4 is one of the two yesses] Since which year do/did you work with this target group?

Since the year:

[Q4b] [If Q4 is 'Yes, I worked with this target group in the past'] **Until and including which year did you work with this target group?** Until and including the year ...:

[Q5] **What is the GMFCS level of the children and/or young adults (8 until and including 25 years old) with CP you mainly work(ed) with?**

GMFCS stands for Gross Motor Function Classification System.

Multiple answers are possible.

- GMFCS level I
- GMFCS level II
- GMFCS level III
- GMFCS level IV
- GMFCS level V
- GMFCS level I do not know (anymore). I do know that the children/young adults with CP whom I work(ed) are not or barely able to speak
- GMFCS level I do not know (anymore). I do know that the children/young adults with CP whom I work(ed) speak well

[If in Q5 none of these three options is selected 'GMFCS level IV, GMFCS level V, GMFCS level I do not know (anymore). I do know that the children/young adults with CP whom I work(ed) are not or barely able to speak']

Thank you for filling in this survey.

The remainder of this survey is aimed at care professionals who work(ed) children/young adults (8 until and including 25 years old) with CP, GMFCS IV and/or V.

[Q6] **In which function do/did you work with this target group?**

	v
Physician or pediatrician	
Occupational therapist	
(Pediatric) Physiotherapist	
Mental healthcare psychologist	
Speech therapist	
Social worker	
(Pediatric) Neurologist	
(Special) Education psychologist/teacher	
Childcare worker	
Pedagogue	
Psychologist (basic, cognitive, neuro-, clinical, other)	
Psycho(motor) therapist	
Treatment coordinator	
(Pediatric) Rehabilitation physician	
Social pedagogical caregiver	
Caregiver	
Nurse	
Care coordinator	
If you have another profession, then you may enter this in the next question	

[Q6a] [If Q6 is '...'] **What is or was your profession with this target group?**

[Q7] In which province do/did you work with this target group (location of the practice or organization)?

v
Drenthe
Flevoland
Friesland
Gelderland
Groningen
Limburg
Noord-Brabant
Noord-Holland
Overijssel
Utrecht
Zeeland
Zuid-Holland
Not in the Netherlands

[Q7a] [If 'Not in the Netherlands'] In which country do/did you work with this target group?

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[Q8] Which type(s) of CP are (mainly) diagnosed in this target group?

- Dyskinetic CP
- Bilateral spastic CP (also called spastic quadriplegia)
- I do not know (anymore)
- Other, namely:

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This is the end of part 1 of the survey. Hereafter follows part 2 of the survey.

[Q9b] In addition, we want to know **how limiting** the by you indicated as present factors are for the communication of the children/young adults with CP GMFCS IV/V you work(ed) with. Below you may order the factors from **most limiting** (at the top/ number 1) to the **least limiting** (bottom). You may order the factors by dragging them to the position where they belong according to you.

[If in Q9a the options '0%' or 'I do not know (anymore)' were not selected for a factor, only then this factor is asked in the ranking question below. This means ranking maximally 12 factors.]

Problems with movements	1
Problems with hearing	2
Problems with seeing	3
Problems with understanding what spoken language	4
Problems with understanding non-verbal signals (e.g. facial expressions, hand gestures)	5
Problems with maintaining attention during a conversation	6
Problems with cognition/ thinking abilities	7
Problems with learning to read or spell	8
The current communication aids are not usable enough for these children/young adults	9
Time limit of the interlocutor(s)	10
The interlocutor(s) do not understand the current communication signals of these children/young adults well enough	11
The current communication aids are not usable enough for the interlocutor(s)	12

[Q9c] If you know one or more factors that limit the communication in these children/young adults, then you may fill in these factors (give a short description of the factor). Please indicate in how many percent of the children/young adults with CP GMFCS IV/V you work(ed) with this factor is present (1-20%, 21-40%, 41-60%, 61-80%, 81-100%). Please also indicate at which position you would rank this factor as you did in the previous question (number 1 = the most limiting factor, the last number = the least limiting).

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Part 2.2: Current communication aids

Below you may select in which way(s) the children/young adults with CP GMFCS IV/V you work(ed) with communicate in general.

There are three categories:

- Without aid, or with a simple aid (such as a lettercard or communication book)
- A simple speech computer (text-device/ static system)
- A high-tech communication aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)

Please mark per category all relevant options.

If a specific category is not applicable for the children with severe CP you work(ed) with, then select '**Not applicable**'.

If you do not know (anymore) whether the category is applicable to the children with severe CP you work(ed) with, then select '**I do not know (anymore)**'.

[Q10a] Category 1: The children with severe CP you work(ed) with communicate without aid, or with a simple aid (such as a lettercard or communication book), by means of:

- Producing sounds, noises or words
- Blinking with the eyes
- Making vertical or horizontal eye movements
- Movements of facial muscles (such as mouth/tongue, and/or eyebrows)
- Movements of hand(s)/finger(s)
- Movements of foot/feet
- Movements of the head
- Using a letterboard/lettercard
- Using a communication book
- The children/young adults I work(ed) with do something else with their body (with or without lettercard/communication book) to communicate, namely:

- Not applicable:** The children/young adults I work(ed) with use none of the above mentioned ways to communicate
- I do not know (anymore):** I selected no answer option(s) above, because I do not know (anymore) whether the children/young adults I work(ed) with communicate this way.

[Q10b]

Category 2: The children you work(ed) with communicate via a simple speech computer (text-device/ static system), which is controlled via:

- Pressing one or multiple buttons
- Other, namely:

- Not applicable:** The children/young adults I work(ed) with do not use a speech computer (text-device/static system) to communicate
- I do not know (anymore):** I selected no answer option(s) above, because I do not know (anymore) whether the children/young adults I work(ed) with communicate via a simple speech computer (text- device/static system).

[Q10c] **Category 3: The children you work(ed) with communicate via a high-tech communication aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system), which is controlled via:**

- Pressing one or multiple buttons
- A mouse/cursor
- A joystick
- A blow-suck switch
- A tongue switch
- A head switch
- A touchscreen
- Eye control (eye tracker)
- A camera (detecting for example mouth- or eyebrow movements)
- Other, namely:

- Not applicable:** The children/young adults I work(ed) with do not use a tablet/computer/dynamic system to communicate
- I do not know (anymore):** I selected no answer option(s) above, because I do not know (anymore) whether the children/young adults I work(ed) with communicate via a tablet/computer/dynamic system.

Part 2.3: Situations current communication aids

Below we ask you in which situations the by you selected categories (max 3) on communication methods are used by the children with severe CP you work(ed) with.

[If Q10a 'Not applicable' and 'I do not know' are not selected]

The following questions are about the category: **Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard.**

[Q11a.1] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard."]

In which location(s) could this way of communicating (without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard) be used in general by the children with severe CP you work(ed) with?

Multiple answers are possible.

- At home
- Other indoor location(s)
- Outdoors
- I do not know (anymore)
- Other, namely:

[Q11a.2] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard."]

With which interlocutor(s) could this way of communicating (without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard) be used in general by the children with severe CP you work(ed) with?

- Maximally 2 people, if familiar and trained
- More than 2 people, if familiar and trained
- More than 2 people, regardless of whether or not trained
- I do not know (anymore)
- Other, namely:

[Q11a.3] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard."]

For which purpose(s) could this way of communicating (without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard) be used in general by the children with severe CP you work(ed) with?

Multiple answers are possible.

- Calling a parent or caregiver
- Functional conversation (for example, exchanging information (such as about the care), or ordering a bread or an ice cream)
- Personal conversation (for example, expressing emotions, talking small talk, discussing with family and friends)
- Education ((home) school)
- Playing games (for example on computer/tablet)
- Expressing artistically (such as drawing, painting, making music, for example on the computer/tablet)
- I do not know (anymore)
- Other, namely:

[Q11a.4] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard."]

We are curious about what you are satisfied or not regarding using this way of communicating (without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard) for communication by the children with severe CP you work(ed) with?

	Yes	Sometimes	No	I do not know (anymore)
It is fast enough to let the user say what (s)he wants to say	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It does what the user wants it to do	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is easy to use by the user	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

[Q11a.1/2/3/4.1] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard."]

If you want to clarify your answers on the location(s), interlocutor(s), purpose(s) and/or the satisfaction, then you may fill this in here:

[Q11a.5] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard."]

How satisfied are you about this way of communicating?

(1 = very unsatisfied, 2 = unsatisfied, 3 = neutral, 4 = satisfied, 5 = very satisfied)

Very unsatisfied (1) (2) (3) (4) Very satisfied (5)

[Q11a.5.1] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard."]

If you want to clarify your answer, then you may fill this in here:

[Q11a.6] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard."]

Which benefits does this way of communicating have according to you?

[Q11a.7] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard."]

Which disadvantages does this way of communicating have according to you?

[If Q10b 'Not applicable' and 'I do not know' are not selected]

The following questions are about the category: **A simple speech computer (text-device/static system)**.

[Q11b.1] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system)."]

In which location(s) could a simple speech computer (text-device/static system) be used in general by the children with severe CP you work(ed) with?

Multiple answers are possible.

- At home
- Other indoor location(s)
- Outdoors
- I do not know (anymore)
- Other, namely:

[Q11b.2] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system)."]

With which interlocutor(s) could a simple speech computer (text-device/static system) be used in general by the children with severe CP you work(ed) with?

- Maximally 2 people, if familiar and trained
- More than 2 people, if familiar and trained
- More than 2 people, regardless of whether or not trained
- I do not know (anymore)
- Other, namely:

[Q11b.3] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system)."]

For which purpose(s) could a simple speech computer (text-device/static system) be used in general by the children with severe CP you work(ed) with?

Multiple answers are possible.

- Calling a parent or caregiver
- Functional conversation (for example, exchanging information (such as about the care), or ordering a bread or an ice cream)
- Personal conversation (for example, expressing emotions, talking small talk, discussing with family and friends)
- Education ((home) school)
- Playing games (for example on computer/tablet)
- Expressing artistically (such as drawing, painting, making music, for example on the computer/tablet)
- I do not know (anymore)
- Other, namely:

[Q11b.4] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system)."]

We are curious about what you are satisfied or not regarding using a simple speech computer (text-device/static system) for communication by the children with severe CP you work(ed) with?

	Yes	No	I do not know
It is fast enough to let te user say what (s)he wants to say	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It does what the user wants it to do	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is fast enough to start	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is easy to use by the user	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

[Q11b.1/2/3/4.1] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system)."]

If you want to clarify your answers on the location(s), interlocutor(s), purpose(s) and/or satisfaction, then you may fill this in here:

[Q11b.5] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system)."]

How satisfied are you about this way of communicating?

(1 = very unsatisfied, 2 = unsatisfied, 3 = neutral, 4 = satisfied, 5 = very satisfied)

Very unsatisfied (1) (2) (3) (4) Very satisfied (5)

[Q11b.5.1] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system)."]

If you want to clarify your answer, then you may fill this in here:

[Q11b.6] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system)."]

Which benefits does this way of communicating have according to you?

[Q11b.7] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system)."]

Which disadvantages does this way of communicating have according to you?

[If Q10c 'Not applicable' and 'I do not know' are not selected]

The following questions are about the category: **A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)**.

[Q11c.1] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)."]

In which location(s) could a high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system) be used in general by the children with severe CP you work(ed) with?

Multiple answers are possible.

- At home
- Other indoor location(s)
- Outdoors
- I do not know (anymore)
- Other, namely:

[Q11c.2] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)."]

With which interlocutor(s) could a high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system) be used in general by the children with severe CP you work(ed) with?

- Maximally 2 people, if familiar and trained
- More than 2 people, if familiar and trained
- More than 2 people, regardless of whether or not trained
- I do not know (anymore)
- Other, namely:

[Q11c.3] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)."]

For which purpose(s) could a high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system) be used in general by the children with severe CP you work(ed) with?

Multiple answers are possible.

- Calling a parent or caregiver
- Functional conversation (for example, exchanging information (such as about the care), or ordering a bread or an ice cream)
- Personal conversation (for example, expressing emotions, talking small talk, discussing with family and friends)
- Education ((home) school)
- Playing games (for example on computer/tablet)
- Expressing artistically (such as drawing, painting, making music, for example on the computer/tablet)
- I do not know (anymore)
- Other, namely:

[Q11c.4] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)."]

We are curious about what you are satisfied or not regarding using a high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system) for communication by the children with severe CP you work(ed) with?

	Yes	No	I do not know
It is fast enough to let the user say what (s)he wants to say	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It does what the user wants it to do	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is fast enough to start	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is easy to use by the user	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

[Q11c.1/2/3/4.1] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)."]

If you want to clarify your answers on location(s), interlocutor(s), purpose(s) and/or satisfaction, then you may fill this in here:

[Q11c.5] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)."]

How satisfied are you about this way of communicating?

(1 = very unsatisfied, 2 = unsatisfied, 3 = neutral, 4 = satisfied, 5 = very satisfied)

Very unsatisfied (1) (2) (3) (4) Very satisfied (5)

[Q11c.5.1] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)."]

If you want to clarify your answer, then you may fill this in here:

[Q11c.6] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)."]

Which benefits does this way of communicating have according to you?

[Q11c.7] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)."]

Which disadvantages does this way of communicating have according to you?

Part 2.4: Wishes and needs

[Q12] If you have an suggestions on the needs, and/or desires for change, in the communication support for children/young adults with CP GMFCS IV and/or V, then you may fill this in here:

This is the end of part 2 of the survey. Hereafter follows part 3 of the survey.

Part 3: Brain-Computer Interface

The following questions are about Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs) in general. A BCI is a technique with which someone could control a device via his/her brain activity.

Part 3.1: BCI experience

[Q13] **Have you heard about BCI in humans (scientifically, not science fiction) before this study? If so, in which way(s) have you heard about BCI?**

Multiple answers are possible.

- Yes, I have tried a BCI myself. (This means, I was the user)
- Yes, I have tested a or used a BCI with someone else as the user (for example a patient/client and/or healthy volunteer)
- Yes, I have seen someone testing or using a BCI (for example in person, TV program, a documentary)
- Yes, I have read about someone testing or using a BCI (for example in a research article/study book, news article)
- No, I did not hear about BCI in humans before (scientifically, not science fiction)

[Q13a] *[If Q13 at least one of the four yesses was selected]*

What is your opinion about that specific BCI?

(1 = very negative, 2 = negative, 3 = neutral, 4 = positive, 5 = very positive)

- Very negative (1) (2) (3) (4) Very positive (5)

[Q13a.1] *[If Q16 at least one of the four yesses was selected]*

If you want to clarify your choice (on which BCI-experience(s), why positive/negative, what type of BCI), then you can do this here:

Part 3.2: BCI in general

This survey specifically concerns communication-BCIs. This means, BCIs aimed at supporting communication

Below you find a short movie explaining what a Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) is and how a BCI works in general.

[Q14] What could a BCI mean for children/young adults with CP, GMFCS IV and/or V, and for which purposes could BCIs be interesting specifically?

Part 3.3: Ways to control a BCI

Below we ask you about the feasibility of BCIs.

Below you find a short movie explaining two ways to operate a BCI. This is about 1) brain responses to visual stimuli, 2) brain activity while imagining or attempting movement.

[Q15] If both ways of controlling a BCI would work equally well, how suitable would you find these ways for children/young adults with CP, GMFCS IV and/or V?

(1 = very unsuitable, 2 = unsuitable, 3 = neutral, 4 = suitable, 5 = very suitable)

	Very unsuitable (1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	Very suitable (5)
Flashing letters/symbols	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Movement imagination or attempting to execute	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

[Q15a] If you want to clarify your choice on these ways to control a BCI, you may fill this in here:

Part 3.4: Ways to measure brain activity

Below you find a short movie explaining two ways to measure brain activity. This is about 1) electrodes on the outside of the head, and 2) implanted electrodes.

[Q16] If both ways of measuring brain activity work equally well, how suitable would you find these ways of measuring for children/young adults with CP GMFCS IV and/or V?

(1 = very unsuitable, 2 = unsuitable, 3 = neutral, 4 = suitable, 5 = very suitable)

	Very unsuitable (1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	Very suitable (5)
Electrodes on the outside of the head (no surgery, daily set-up, visible for others because the electrodes are placed on the head)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Implanted electrodes (a surgery, no daily set-up, not visible for others because the electrodes lay under the skull)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

[Q16a] If you want to clarify your choice on these ways to measure, you may fill this in here:

Part 3.5: Comments

[Q17] If you know other target groups, children/young adults with another condition than CP, for whom a BCI for communication would be interesting or supporting, you may fill this in here:

[Q18] Finally, if you have any comments, ideas or suggestions, you may fill this in here:

This is the end of the survey.

If you want to change anything in your answers, you could go back in the survey now. After you click 'next', you cannot change your answers anymore and your answers will be saved.

I give my permission to contact me after this study to ask whether I want to participate in a follow-up study.

Yes No

Would you like to know the results after finishing the research?

Yes No

[If at least one of the two questions above is answered with 'Yes'] Below you may enter your email address to which we may contact you:

Thank you very much for completing the survey!

If you want to keep posted on the developments in the field of CP, then you could sign-up for the newsletter of CP Nederland:

<https://cpnederland.nl/actueel/nieuwsbrieven/>

Are you interested in research in the field of BCI in children/young adults? Take a look at our website:

<https://www.neurosafari.nl/>

The videos in this survey were made by graphical designer Merel Horsmeier.

